

Activism in mathematics education research: Stopping epistemicide by confronting and resisting modern forms of epistemic violence: A response to Aldo Parra

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In this paper, I will share my reaction and evoked thoughts inspired by Aldo's paper. I will argue about modern forms of epistemicide and how particular groups of people have historically lost the condition of humans to the eye of privileged groups. From a Postcolonial perspective, epistemicide problematizes how knowledge is, and has been used, to exert power according to national and global ideas for progress. Such ideas invalidate knowledge produced outside the boundaries of well-founded western forms of scientific practice. Violence against the Other in the path of organizing behaviour implies not only epistemological injustice but a systematic destruction—involving colonization, oppression and genocide. Here, the role of math education researchers should take a turn to give voice to those that have been silenced.

Have you watched the anime *The Promised Neverland*? This anime unravels the story of an orphanage in the year 2045. The orphanage was settled as part of “The promise” agreement made in 1045. Humans and demons set this agreement to keep both worlds—the human world and the demon world—separated. Demons eat humans, so the agreement was to create human breeding farms disguised as orphanages to provide food for the demons. In these orphanages, children believe they are orphans and have to stay in these houses until they get adopted. They are taught that they will be qualified for adoption if they acquire a certain level of intelligence and age. They learn all kinds of things, and, of course, they learn mathematics. When they get “adopted”, they pack their belongings, have a farewell party, and leave the household thinking they will finally be free. Although you can probably see where this is going, they are murdered and sold as meat. They learn how to act and behave, how to eat and what to know, only to be profitable for the meat industry. And, well, this analogy could be as literal as your frame of reference makes you believe. But there is something I've been struggling with for quite some time now—and Aldo Parra's (2021) paper invites me to problematize—: how do we end up believing that mathematics is and should be universal at the cost of annihilating other forms of knowledge? How do we end up believing that epistemicide was the safest bet for economic progress? How do we end up using mathematically justified models to commit genocide—i.e., war math models to calculate how many people can be killed if a bomb is detonated in a certain location? How do we end up using mathematic

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illiteracy as an advantage to commit abuse—i.e., Aldo’s example of tax increase in Colombia? And so, this is my reaction and evoked thoughts inspired by Aldo’s paper.

One of the firsts things that come to my mind when trying to understand how we move in life through desire is the capitalist ideology that leads us to think we have to do what we do to be successful in the global world. One has to have a good job to have a good life. To have a good job, one has to have a promising career. To have a promising career, one has to have good grades and high levels of proficiency in particular school subjects, such as mathematics and science. Did we ever think as kids that the path we take was to become a productive citizen? Probably you didn’t, me neither. But here we are, privileged by knowledge, socially validated as productive. Žižek talks about this with this example, people are more aware of the environmental impact of their choices. Hence, they decide to buy products that won’t generate much waste (no plastic involved, ethically made, cruelty-free, and so on). The industry then starts marketing products that should respond to people’s needs. If someone goes to the supermarket and buys a fair-trade chocolate bar with a paper wrap over a bar of plastic-wrapped chocolate, did this person do something to combat the environmental impact of food consumption? The industry with fancy labels—and so on—doesn’t tell that, sometimes, paper wraps have a plastic coat to preserve some foods and to avoid moisture (who will buy a chocolate bar with a wet paper wrap?). This is why desire is intriguing. I watched the documentary *Seaspiracy* and saw how “dolphin-safe” labels are put into tuna cans when there is no certainty if dolphins were killed or not in the process. But people buy these products because of sustainable wildlife preservation. In this regard, Žižek says desire comes from fantasy. The fantasy keeps us in a constant state of desiring, probably feeling incomplete or an impulse of belonging.

We are constantly validated according to what we can give to society intellectually, financially, you name it! For instance, I don’t see myself doing anything else than teaching, researching and being the best mom I can possibly be for my daughter. Do I talk to anyone about how epistemicide leads to perceive diversity as a threat to school mathematics? I write papers about it (and receive my monetary incentive for publications), go to conferences, give lectures without much result of being labelled as a pessimist by some mathematics educators or be well-received by my peers and mentors (probably reading this reaction). Aldo’s paper presents experiences from other fellow researchers worldwide resisting and confronting epistemological violence and the use of mathematically justified forms to commit abuse to segregated and historically marginalized groups. This is done not behind a desk and a screen as I do, but in the front line. In academia, what we do is silenced, arguing what we do is not valid scientific research. They do not publish our work, even if we have enough data to make our claims clear and justified. What we do is not considered proper math education research. We live marginalized in the shadows of mathematics education. One of the main conclusions I got from Aldo’s discussion is that it is not enough by recognizing forms of violence and the interplay they have with mathematics (either to help mathematically or to show how school mathematics alienates groups of people). It is not enough by doing research or problematizing the *status quo*. One should become a mathematics educator activist, as David Bowers (2021, in this volume, also commenting on Aldo’s paper).

The second thing that came to mind is how power has been historically exerted through knowledge. I mean, it is not about how many things someone knows (for example, Nasa's knowledge in Aldo's discussion), but if people learn the right things to be validated in contemporaneity (if people qualify for "adoption" or not). Historically, a systematic epistemicide of particular groups of people have led them to lose the condition of humans to the eye of privileged groups, for example, indigenous people to the eye of colonizers. From a Postcolonial perspective, epistemicide problematizes how knowledge is, and has been used, to exert power according to national and global ideas for progress. Such ideas invalidate knowledge that is produced outside the boundaries of well-founded western forms of scientific practice: the taken as valid forms of knowledge. Here, the role of mathematics education researchers should take a turn to give voice to the abused, segregated, marginalized and invisibilized.

Globalization does not set equitable knowledge levels to all but to produce and naturalize forms of epistemic violence to communities that don't share validated capitalistic practices, conducts, and desires. Then, they must strike for survival only because they share other cosmologies than the "normal" and conceive mathematics in other ways. Here, a fine line between the right of remaining silent and the silencing of voices (either rhetorical or literal) decides people's future and attitude to engage with formal forms of schooling and towards learning school mathematics. I wonder how much mathematics a Mapuche kid could learn if their families and communities are portrayed as terrorists by the media and if their communities are constantly attacked and killed. Then, it is a bit obvious, at least for me, that they are not going to perform well in national standardized tests. (Please, I invite you to search the internet for "police brutality against Mapuche children" or "Mapuche children injured by police".) Their fight is not about equitable access to education but the right to live without life-threatening attacks. In such contexts, school mathematics is far away from saving Mapuche children lives. Is it enough by publishing about their cultural richness and mathematical knowledge they have? Should we partake in helping to solve the conflict between authorities taking over Mapuche lands and Mapuche families defending their territories? What is our role as mathematic researcher activists? Is it enough by researching multiculturalism, multilingualism, inclusion, equity, agency, social justice, and so on? Is it enough by giving voice to the voiceless (as Aldo once said when we were PhD students)? Should I share Mapuche experiences to make visible the lack of conditions and foregrounds, in Ole Skovsmose' terms, they have?

En un allanamiento la agresividad es impactante, pocas veces hemos podido registrar imágenes donde Carabineros golpea a un niño, golpea a una mujer con una niña en brazos. Que tu casa esté llena de lacrimógenas al interior y tengas que salir producto del ahogo o ver a tu padre lleno de perdigones y sangrando por todos lados, son cosas que impactan mucho a un niño. Impactan a cualquier persona", dice Mijael Carbone. (Unrepresented Nations & Peoples Organization [UNPO], 2015)

In a raid, the aggressiveness is shocking; we have rarely been able to record images where the Police hit a child, hits a woman with a girl in her arms. That your house is full of tear gas inside, and you must come out because you cannot breathe or seeing your father full of pellets and bleeding from all sides. These are things that greatly impact a child. They impact anyone," says Mijael Carbone. (UNPO, 2015, my translation)

In 2011, three NGOs demanded Chile for violence and child abuse, so the Supreme Court ordered not to apply the Antiterrorist Law to children. Although, everything remained the same.

En el último informe anual de la institución, publicado a comienzos de 2015, se lee: “las violaciones de derechos –en particular de niños/as y adolescentes mapuche– producto del uso excesivo de la fuerza por parte de personal de Carabineros, se ha mantenido a lo largo del año sin mayores cambios en un patrón sobre el cual el INDH ha reclamado, y al cual se ha referido la justicia, en el sentido de cuestionar y sancionar el actuar de las fuerzas de seguridad, particularmente respecto de niños y niñas mapuche, exigiendo su apego irrestricto a las normas y reglamentos vigentes”. El INDH ya expresó su preocupación al Comité de los Derechos del Niño de la ONU, que hizo público el recién pasado 2 de octubre [2015] un documento con observaciones y sugerencias respecto a la infancia al Estado de Chile. Allí declara que “El Comité sigue profundamente preocupado por la situación permanente de la desigualdad, la discriminación y la violencia contra los niños indígenas, en particular los niños mapuches”. (UNPO, 2015)

In the last institution’s annual report, published at the beginning of 2015, it is written: “the violations of rights –particularly of Mapuche children and adolescents– as a result of the excessive use of force by Carabineros, have been maintained throughout the year without major changes in such a way that the NHRI has complained, and to which justice has referred, in the sense of questioning and sanctioning the actions of the police, particularly with regard to Mapuche children, demanding their unrestricted adherence to the current rules and regulations”. The INDH has already expressed its concern to the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child, which published on October 2 [2015] a document with observations and suggestions regarding children to the State of Chile. There it states that “The Committee remains deeply concerned about the permanent situation of inequality, discrimination and violence against indigenous children, in particular Mapuche children”. (UNPO, 2015, my translation)

Violence against the *Other* in the path of organizing behaviour and the quest for social order implies not only epistemological injustice but a systematic destruction—involving colonization, oppression and even genocide. So, what role can we play as mathematic education activists against epistemological violence? I still wonder.

Not only have indigenous groups experienced these practices, but women have also been alienated from mathematic practices, believing that women should not be educated. In Chile, the firsts school for women were not meant for them to actively participate in society but in learning how to be a good mother and wife. The mathematics they knew were not meant for them to pursue an academic life but to be able to help their kids with their homework. What contributions could women make if they were not authorized to engage in mathematician discussions? Women’s mathematical knowledge was not allowed to exist. Although, when it comes to ethnic differences, other marginalized groups suffered brutal forms of violence (not only epistemic violence). Black slaves who came to Chile, not by choice (sold as products), were not even considered humans. They were reduced to serve the white men and lose the opportunity to access the spaces reserved only for the elite, such as schools. There were even discussions about “reproduction of Black populations” that proposed forced sterilization of

most Black people. In other parts of the globe, these white men supremacy included also forced sterilization of indigenous groups.

Losing humans' condition and being taken as a body (without agency or else) from which other people can decide (i.e., pro-choice versus pro-life debates about abortion) is much more than just school mathematics. But it should concern mathematics education activists. Mathematics is constantly used as a form of disseminating statistical results about everything, and people read it. More often, those numbers or graphs are manipulated for people to take directed decisions—this is when math illiteracy is used to commit abuse. Meanwhile, math is advertised as the key to escape from these unlivable spaces in educational policies and transnational reports. People should be empowered by mathematics; then, they will be able to read news and not be fooled by the media and take an informed decision. However, people wouldn't have to be empowered by math if the media didn't use maths to misinform and scandalized the public. What is our role as mathematics education activists here? Should we point to every time the press commits these abuses and explain why the numbers and graphs are adulterated? Does anyone care about charts at this point? As Aldo says, clickbait is created for the morbid audience to obtain profit from some random website: why informing people when you can make money from urgent, paradoxical and scandalous content, right? The wonders of school mathematics are another form of click bait. We have to ask who benefits from these classroom practices, is it children? I believe they don't.

Finally, I'm not comfortable with the idea of doing something if it makes sense for us, even if it doesn't turn out well, because that is the same train of thought that evangelization in Latin America was framed. They were saving us from our doom, from going to hell, whatever. We need to find a middle ground between not imposing our beliefs on *Others*, not alienating the *Other*. Probably Emmanuel Levinas could help in setting school mathematics from *Otherness* (*alteridad* in Spanish). We have so many possible paths to take from here, but I will start by challenging the assumption that all people need mathematics (and the same type of mathematics) for success. I mean, why mathematics? What mathematics? When mathematics? And for whom? We should challenge those political and economic decisions as mathematics education research activists to confront and resist modern forms of epistemic violence.

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